

Phase1 - Interview Script

Intro

- About myself and the project
- Information sheet and consent form
- Is it ok if I record the interview
- Feel free to elaborate on any details that come to mind
- How much time do you have?

Background

- Work - Please present yourself
- Relationship to new technologies

If MD:

- How do you diagnose MS?
- How do you monitor/follow-up patients with MS?
- How much time do you have available to diagnose, follow-up on patients with MS?
- What tools do you use for diagnosis and monitoring? What do you think of them (like/dislike/missing/trust)? Maybe specifically ask for pros and cons of the tools mentioned?
- What kind of tools would help you to monitor patients / help you for diagnosis?
 - If they do not mention MRI, ask why
 - And if they do mention MRI, specifically asks which contrasts do they use
- Which aspect(s) of monitoring / diagnosing patients do you consider to be the most challenging? How could these be simplified?
- What aspects of diagnosis and/or monitoring must, in your opinion, be completed manually? (i.e. could not be improved with automation)
- How familiar are you with artificial intelligence, and more specifically deep-learning techniques? What is your perception of the use of these tools in the context of healthcare? (If only positives/negatives, do you have any negative/positive points that you would also like to add?)
- What do you think the word uncertainty means?
- What do you think the word saliency means?

If Engineer:

- What tools do you know for MS diagnosis and monitoring?
- What tools do you know for MS MR image analysis?
- What do you think of existing tools for diagnosis and monitoring (how useful, how easy to use, current drawbacks)?

- What opinions have physicians around you emitted on existing diagnostic and/or monitoring tools? Do you tend to agree or disagree with these opinions?
- What kind of tools do you think would help to monitor patients / help for diagnosis?
- How do you think deep-learning tools can be integrated in the clinical workflow?
- What are the challenges in developing such tools?
- What is your opinion of Explainable AI?

Finish

- Thank you for your time!
- Would you be interested and/or available in taking part in the second phase of the study, which consists in a user test?